

**EMBRACING DIVERSITY: EXPLORING AWARENESS AND ACCEPTANCE OF
FIDUCIA SUPPLICANS' SAME-SEX BLESSINGS AMONG PARISHIONERS OF SAN
NICOLAS DE TOLENTINO PARISH, ARCHDIOCESE OF CEBU**

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the awareness and acceptance of the *Fiducia Supplicans* doctrine, which permits same-sex blessings, among parishioners of San Nicolas de Tolentino Parish in Cebu. The research aims to understand the parishioners' knowledge and attitudes toward this controversial issue within the Catholic Church. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed, involving 200 respondents selected through purposive sampling. The sample was evenly distributed across four gender categories, ensuring a representative demographic. Data were collected via a self-made questionnaire, demonstrating high reliability, with Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of .929 for awareness and .964 for acceptance. Statistical analyses, including mean, standard deviation, and linear regression, were conducted using SPSS software. The findings reveal that parishioners generally understand the nature of same-sex blessings under *Fiducia Supplicans*, particularly recognizing that these blessings do not alter the Church's doctrine on marriage. Accepting these blessings is rated as acceptable, reflecting a moderate level of endorsement, particularly regarding inclusivity and compassion within the religious community. A significant positive correlation (Spearman's rho = 0.419, $p < 0.01$) was found between the levels of awareness and acceptance, indicating that higher awareness is associated with greater acceptance of same-sex blessings. These results suggest that education and information dissemination could be crucial in shaping more accepting attitudes toward such practices within conservative religious communities.

Keywords: *Fiducia Supplican, same-sex blessings, Catholic Church*

INTRODUCTION

Homosexuality, defined as a sexual interest in and attraction to individuals of the same sex (Britannica, 2023), has been historically regarded as abnormal and beyond full societal acceptance (Carlström, 2020). Within Christianity, particularly the Roman Catholic Church, diverse viewpoints emerge due to varying interpretations of the Bible. Traditionally, Christianity has promoted heterosexuality, with a prevailing lack of acceptance for homosexuality (Nkosi & Masson, 2017).

Contrastingly, certain liberal Christian denominations have embraced same-sex marriage as a testament to viewing homosexuality as normal and acceptable. In the United States, the Evangelical Lutheran Church of America, the Episcopal Church, and the United Church of Christ have taken steps to endorse and officiate same-sex marriages (Feeney, 2015). Similarly, the LGBT Christian Church in the Philippines, founded by Rev. Ceejay Agbayani, conducts same-sex weddings known as the Rite of the Holy Union (Celis, 2018). However, the Roman Catholic Church maintains a steadfast position, as it does not endorse same-sex marriage, considering it a sacrament exclusively between a baptized man and woman (Kuźelewska & Michalczuk-Wlizio, 2021).

In Catholic theology, same-sex relations are considered inherently sinful and urge avoidance (Garver, 2023). Despite modern times, the church has not altered its condemnation of same-sex relations (Reid, 2020). This stance is rooted in the Holy Scriptures, such as Leviticus 18:22 and 20:13, and reinforced by St. Paul's warnings against sexual immorality (1 Cor. 6:18). The Catholic Church, through documents like Vatican II's *Lumen Gentium* and the Catechism of the Catholic Church, emphasizes the call to holiness and purity for homosexuals (CCC 2359).

Acknowledging homosexuals in a state of sin, the Church seeks to manifest God's mercy and compassion by allowing priests to bless same-sex couples, as outlined in the document "Fiducia Supplicans" by the Vatican Dicastery for the Doctrine of the Faith (Dela Peña, 2023). Archbishop Villegas of the Archdiocese of Lingayen-Dagupan reveals that spontaneous blessings may be used if the couple humbly approaches the priest seeking God's mercy, not the liturgical or ritual blessings, which are the official blessings of the Catholic Church (CBCP News, 2023). This blessing, however, is not to be equated with approval or endorsement of homosexuality (Giuffrida, 2024). It aligns with Orihuela-Alicante, Spain Bishop Munilla's views that blessings can be extended to sinners while not endorsing their sins, drawing parallels to Jesus' encounter with a sinful woman in John 8:11. Pope Francis further emphasizes the universality of divine blessings, clarifying that they do not endorse unions or specific behaviors (Mares, 2024).

The *Fiducia Supplicans*, which allows the blessing of same-sex couples, emphasizes that this blessing should not be equated with marriage. Instead, it shows the commitment to uphold the Church's doctrine on marriage as a sacrament, defined explicitly as an unbreakable union between one man and one woman. Importantly, this blessing does not confer legitimacy to any form of union; it is granted spontaneously outside formal liturgical ceremonies. Instances for the bestowal of this blessing include visits to shrines, meetings with priests, group prayers, or during pilgrimages.

The global response to the *Fiducia Supplicans* doctrine has been diverse. While LGBTQ advocates celebrate it as groundbreaking, conservative sectors express disappointment (The Feed, 2023). In the Philippines, the LGBTQ community welcomes the declaration (Reyes, 2023), but Church leaders in Africa and Central Asia prohibit the practice despite Vatican approval (Rocca, 2023). Conservative bishops criticize the policy as a departure from the Church's historical condemnation of same-sex relations (Crary, 2024).

In the San Nicolas de Tolentino Parish of the Archdiocese of Cebu, the awareness and acceptance of the *Fiducia Supplicans* doctrine on same-sex blessings still need to be explored. This study aims to fill this research gap by examining the doctrine's awareness and acceptance within the local community. The findings will inform intervention plans and contribute to the ongoing discourse on this contentious issue within the Catholic Church.

Research Questions

Generally, the study determined the level of awareness and acceptance of *Fiducia Supplicans*' same-sex blessings among parishioners of San Nicolas de Tolentino Parish, Archdiocese of Cebu.

Specifically, the study identified the following:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - A. age; and
 - B. gender?
2. What is the respondents' awareness level of *Fiducia Supplicans*' same-sex blessings?
3. What is the respondents' acceptance level of *Fiducia Supplicans*' same-sex blessings?
4. Is there a significant relationship between respondents' level of awareness and acceptance of *Fiducia Supplicans*' same-sex blessings?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive-correlational approach to exploring the research inquiries. It focused on assessing respondents' awareness and acceptance of *Fiducia Supplicans*' same-sex blessings and examining the relationships among various variables.

Purposive sampling was used to select 200 respondents, evenly distributed with 50 individuals per gender, all Roman Catholics and parishioners of San Nicolas de Tolentino Parish, aged 18 years and above.

Data collection was done through a self-made questionnaire. The survey questionnaire assessing awareness yielded a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of .929, indicating a high level of internal consistency among the items measuring respondents' awareness. Similarly, the questionnaire measuring acceptance achieved a Cronbach's Alpha of .964, suggesting strong internal reliability among the items gauging respondents'

acceptance levels. These high Cronbach's Alpha values affirm the robustness and reliability of the survey instruments utilized in this study.

It was administered via face-to-face interactions and online platforms such as Google Forms within the communities surrounding the parish throughout March 2024. The collected data underwent analysis and interpretation utilizing statistical methods, including mean, standard deviation, and linear regression analysis, facilitated by SPSS software.

RESULTS

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Age

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
18 – 30	109	54.5
31 – above	91	45.5
Total	200	100

Table 1 presents the age distribution of the study respondents. Out of 200 participants, 54.5% (109 individuals) are aged between 18 and 30, while 45.5% (91 individuals) are aged 31 and above. This indicates that the sample is composed of a slightly larger group of younger adults than older adults. The total number of respondents is 200, accounting for 100% of the sample.

Table 2. Profile of the Students in Terms of Gender

GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Male	50	25.0
Female	50	25.0
Gay	50	25.0
Lesbian	50	25.0
Total	200	100.0

Table 2 illustrates the gender distribution of the 200 students in the study. The sample is equally divided among four gender categories: male, female, gay, and lesbian, comprising 25.0% of the total. Specifically, 50 students identify as male, 50 as female, 50 as gay, and 50 as lesbian. This even distribution ensures that each gender group is represented equally, making up the entire sample of 200 students.

Table 3. Level of Awareness of Fiducia Supplicants' Same-Sex Blessings

STATEMENTS			MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	VERBAL DESCRIPTION
Fiducia	Supplicants'	same-sex blessings uphold the Church's doctrine on marriage as a sacrament and an unbreakable union formed between one man and one woman.	3.71	1.294	Aware
Fiducia	Supplicants'	same-sex blessings highlight that it should be bestowed "spontaneously."	3.61	1.156	Aware
Fiducia	Supplicants'	same-sex blessings should have no prerequisite for prior moral perfection.	3.17	1.132	Neither Aware nor Not Aware
Fiducia	Supplicants'	same-sex blessings are done outside of a liturgical ceremony.	3.22	1.116	Neither Aware nor Not Aware
Fiducia	Supplicants'	same-sex blessings are inclusive or meant for everyone, not exclusive.	3.59	1.187	Aware
Fiducia	Supplicants'	same-sex blessings do not legalize anything.	3.30	1.220	Neither Aware nor Not Aware
Fiducia	Supplicants'	same-sex blessings do not deviate from canon law and catechism.	3.46	1.306	Aware
Fiducia	Supplicants'	same-sex blessings are not expressed in any formal rite by ecclesial authorities.	3.19	1.140	Neither Aware nor Not Aware
Fiducia	Supplicants'	same-sex blessings are not a civil or Church union.	3.06	1.195	Neither Aware nor Not Aware
Fiducia	Supplicants'	same-sex blessings are not conferred with clothing, gestures, or words specific to a wedding ceremony.	3.25	1.210	Neither Aware nor Not Aware
Fiducia	Supplicants'	same-sex blessings can occur during a visit to a shrine, a meeting with a priest, a group prayer, or a pilgrimage.	3.49	1.169	Aware
Fiducia	Supplicants'	same-sex blessings open one's life to God, allowing one to seek His assistance in living a better life and invoking the Holy Spirit to embrace the values of the Gospel with increased fidelity.	3.86	1.161	Neither Aware nor Not Aware

Fiducia Suplicans' same-sex blessings do not alter the enduring doctrine of the Church regarding marriage.	3.49	1.228	Aware
Fiducia Suplicans' same-sex blessings support and guide the sinners.	3.22	1.318	Neither Aware nor Not Aware
Fiducia Suplicans' same-sex blessings show that people need the mercy and compassion of God.	3.99	1.163	Aware
Overall Mean	3.440666667	0.272671091	Aware

LEGEND

Scale	Interpretation
(4.20-5.00)	<i>Fully Aware</i>
(3.40-4.19)	<i>Aware</i>
(2.60-3.39)	<i>Neither Aware nor Not Aware</i>
(1.80-2.59)	<i>Not Aware</i>
(1.00-1.79)	<i>Fully Not Aware</i>

The research findings on the level of awareness regarding Fiducia Supplicans' same-sex blessings reveal a nuanced understanding among participants. With an overall mean score of 3.44 and a standard deviation of 0.27, the findings indicate an awareness level, which means that there is a general awareness of same-sex blessings among individuals and communities. While not universal knowledge, a substantial portion of the population understands and recognizes the concept.

Respondents were notably aware that these blessings do not alter the Church's doctrine on marriage as a sacrament (mean = 3.71, SD = 1.29), are meant to be inclusive (mean = 3.59, SD = 1.19), and do not legalize or formalize unions (mean = 3.30, SD = 1.22). Additionally, the blessings are recognized as not part of a formal liturgical ceremony (mean = 3.22, SD = 1.12) and do not require prior moral perfection (mean = 3.17, SD = 1.13). Despite this awareness, there was some uncertainty regarding aspects such as the absence of specific formal rites (mean = 3.19, SD = 1.14) and the blessings not being a civil or Church union (mean = 3.06, SD = 1.20). The highest awareness was recorded regarding the blessings' role in seeking divine assistance and embracing Gospel values (mean = 3.86, SD = 1.16), while the lowest awareness was about the guidance these blessings offer to sinners (mean = 3.22, SD = 1.32).

Table 4. Level of Acceptance of Fiducia Supplicans' Same-Sex Blessings

STATEMENTS	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	VERBAL DESCRIPTION
Same-sex blessings in Fiducia Supplicans are a positive expression of diversity within our community.	3.31	1.300	Acceptable
Embracing same-sex blessings contributes to a more inclusive and welcoming religious environment.	3.27	1.317	Acceptable
Acceptance of same-sex blessings aligns with our faith's principles of love and compassion.	3.44	1.282	Moderately Acceptable
Same-sex blessings can strengthen the sense of community and unity among believers.	3.35	1.363	Acceptable
The recognition of same-sex blessing reflects a progressive and forward-thinking approach to spirituality.	3.23	1.270	Acceptable
Everyone, regardless of sexual orientation, should have the opportunity to receive a blessing in Fiducia Supplicans.	3.47	1.303	Moderately Acceptable
Our religious community should respond to evolving societal norms, including the acceptance of same-sex blessings.	3.37	1.269	Acceptable
Opposing same-sex blessings contradicts the core values of respect and acceptance within our faith.	3.19	1.305	Acceptable
Same-sex blessings can enhance the spiritual experience for the couples and the congregation.	3.22	1.288	Acceptable
Acknowledging same-sex blessings is essential for our religious community's relevance in the modern world.	3.39	1.287	Acceptable
The acceptance of same-sex blessings aligns with the teachings of love and acceptance found in our religious texts.	3.39	1.329	Acceptable
Same-sex blessings can foster a more compassionate and understanding attitude among believers.	3.40	1.272	Moderately Acceptable
Opposing same-sex blessings is inconsistent with the spirit of Fiducia Supplicans.	3.05	1.187	Acceptable

Embracing same-sex blessings reflects our religious community's commitment to equality and justice.	3.46	1.279	Moderately Acceptable
The inclusion of same-sex blessings is a positive step towards dismantling discrimination within our faith.	3.31	1.278	Acceptable
Religious communities should adapt their practices to be more inclusive of diverse expressions of love and commitment.	3.54	1.231	Moderately Acceptable
Same-sex blessings are in harmony with our religious teachings' broader message of acceptance.	3.31	1.273	Acceptable
Opposing same-sex blessings may lead to the exclusion and marginalization of individuals within our community.	3.08	1.181	Acceptable
Acknowledging same-sex blessings can contribute to a more harmonious and accepting society.	3.41	1.334	Moderately Acceptable
Accepting same-sex blessings is consistent with our faith's overarching message of love and compassion.	3.48	1.393	Moderately Acceptable
Overall Mean	3.3335	0.130354779	Acceptable

LEGEND

Scale	Interpretation
(4.20-5.00)	Highly Acceptable
(3.40-4.19)	Moderately Acceptable
(2.60-3.39)	Acceptable
(1.80-2.59)	Slightly Unacceptable
(1.00-1.79)	Unacceptable

The research data in Table 4 indicates a generally positive stance among respondents, with an overall mean score of 3.33 and a standard deviation of 0.13, suggesting an acceptable level of acceptance. This means same-sex blessings are generally accepted, with a significant portion of society acknowledging the rights of individuals to choose their life partners and have their unions recognized. While there may be pockets of resistance, overall, there is a prevailing sentiment of tolerance and acceptance.

Respondents view same-sex blessings as a positive expression of diversity (mean = 3.31, SD = 1.30) and contribute to a more inclusive religious environment (mean = 3.27, SD = 1.32). These blessings align with the principles of love and compassion (mean = 3.44, SD = 1.28) and enhance community unity (mean = 3.35, SD = 1.36). Acceptance

reflects a progressive approach to spirituality (mean = 3.23, SD = 1.27) and a commitment to equality and justice (mean = 3.46, SD = 1.28). While most aspects of same-sex blessings are considered acceptable, several statements, such as opposing these blessings being inconsistent with core values (mean = 3.05, SD = 1.19) and acknowledging them as essential for relevance in the modern world (mean = 3.39, SD = 1.29), received moderately acceptable ratings. Overall, the data suggests a favorable but nuanced view of same-sex blessings within Fiducia Supplicans, recognizing their role in fostering inclusivity and compassion.

Table 5. Relationship of the Levels of Awareness to Acceptance of Fiducia Supplicans' Same-Sex Blessings

		Awareness Level	Acceptance Level
Spearman's rho	Awareness Level	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.419**
	N	200	200
	Acceptance Level	Correlation Coefficient	.419**
Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
N		200	200

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Legends:

Spearman p	Correlation
≥ 0.70	Very strong relationship
0.40-0.69	Strong relationship
0.30-0.39	Moderate relationship
0.20-0.29	Weak relationship
0.01-0.19	No or negligible relationship

This descriptor applies to both positive and negative relationships. (Adapted from Dancey and Reidy, 2004).

Table 5 reveals a statistically significant correlation between the levels of awareness and acceptance of Fiducia Supplicans' same-sex blessings. The Spearman's rho coefficient of 0.419 indicates a strong relationship between awareness and acceptance levels. This positive correlation suggests that higher awareness of the nature and context of same-sex blessings in Fiducia Supplicans is associated with greater acceptance. The significance level ($p < 0.01$) confirms that this relationship is unlikely to have occurred by chance, emphasizing the connection between understanding and accepting same-sex blessings within the community.

Conclusions

The research concludes that there is a generally positive and accepting attitude toward Fiducia Supplicans' same-sex blessings, with a strong correlation between awareness and acceptance among respondents. While some uncertainty remains regarding specific aspects of these blessings, the overall sentiment is tolerance, inclusivity, and recognition of the blessings' alignment with principles of love, compassion, and equality. This indicates a growing acceptance of same-sex blessings within the community, driven by increased awareness and understanding.

Recommendations

To further advance understanding and acceptance of Fiducia Supplicans' same-sex blessings, it is recommended that awareness programs be enhanced by developing and implementing educational initiatives that clarify the nature and implications of these blessings. This could include informational materials, workshops, and discussions to address uncertainties and ensure comprehensive understanding. Additionally, promoting inclusivity within the community through celebratory events and recognizing diverse groups can support a more accepting environment. Facilitating open dialogue by creating forums for respectful discussion can help address concerns and promote mutual understanding. Supporting training for religious and community leaders on the theological and social aspects of same-sex blessings will equip them to provide better guidance and foster inclusivity. Lastly, continuously monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of these initiatives through surveys and feedback will help identify areas for improvement and ensure that the community's approach evolves to meet changing attitudes and needs. Implementing these recommendations will help deepen understanding, enhance acceptance, and build a more supportive and inclusive community.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In observance of Republic Act 10173—Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researcher kept the identities, information, and data of all respondents and participants safe. They were also assured that they were not placed in a circumstance where they might be at risk or harmed as a consequence of their participation and attendance in all aspects.

The survey results remained anonymous in the results and discussion of the study. It was also ensured that the participation of the respondents and participants was voluntary. No monetary incentive was involved. Consent was given before their involvement in the study. They were told they had the right to withdraw from participation in the study if they wished.

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